
GUIDELINES FOR BIM INFORMATION MANAGEMENT AT DESIGN STAGE

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Abstract

Information Management in Building Information Modelling (BIM) deals with the quality and efficiency on the retrieval, storage, use and sharing of information throughout the project lifecycle.

The detailed planning, definition of roles and responsibilities, assessment of capabilities, and stating requirements should be established since the very beginning of the project to achieve an effective management of the information of the whole process. However, even if many companies are using BIM tools, lots of them have still not implemented standardised information processes.

This work created a framework to support companies in BIM projects, specifically during the Design Stage, to lead them to a structured management of the information generated during this stage and to prepare its handover.

To do so, in-depth research was conducted on published papers and articles, BIM guides and applicable Standards to gather the best practices in the field and propose guidelines to support a structured BIM adoption in a company's project. It was created a specific workflow based on the Integrated Project Delivery methodology to support companies in BIM adoption. From there, several tools were proposed to assist the BIM Manager in establishing protocols during the project Design Stage. The proposed framework may be used to support companies in assessing and selecting the right team members capabilities, in collecting information requirements efficiently, in establishing a proper BIM Execution Plan and evaluating CDE platforms.

This work was developed in collaboration with a BIM consulting company, allowing for a parallel validation process of this workflow and documents throughout the way.

These tools and the designed workflow are intended to help companies to accelerate their BIM processes, foster collaboration between all the stakeholders, assuring enhanced information management and therefore contributing to the quality of the output and general performance of the organisation.

Dissertation:

https://bimaplus.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/2020-GiuliaTerrosi-Dissertation_compressed.pdf

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/3rYz5eW49JE>

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